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The Effect of two Injectors on SWIR Electron-injection Detector Optoelectrical Characteristics

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Abstract- In this paper, the structure of an electron-injection (EI) infrared detector with two electron injectors is presented, and the electrical and optical characteristics of the proposed device are compared with an EI detector with a single injector. The proposed detectors have an InP injector with a length of 550 nm and an InGaAs absorber with a length of 1 μm . The results indicate that the dark current of the two-injector EI detector is reduced by 61% compared to the single-injector EI detector at a voltage of -3 volt. Although the optical gain of the two-injector EI detector is lower than that of EI detectors with a single injector, its rise time at an optical power of 60 pW is four times faster, making these devices more suitable for high-speed applications.

Keywords: Electron Injection Detector, Dark Current, Optical Gain, Rise Time

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1. Introduction

Sensitive short-wave-infrared (SWIR) photon detectors play an important role in many modern world applications spanning diverse fields, such as quantum cryptography, astronomy, optical tomography, biophotonics and light detection and ranging (LIDAR) [1], [2].

Existing photon-type SWIR detectors currently affordable are mainly based on III-V materials such as InGaAs PIN detectors [3], avalanche photodetectors (APDs) [4] and phototransistor detectors (PTD) [5]. InGaAs PIN detectors have very low leakage current with high speed response but the lack of an internal amplification mechanism limits their application [6]. Avalanche photodetectors are designed based on an internal amplification mechanism but their unpredictable nature of avalanche multiplication process negatively affects gain stability at high values and increases amplitude uncertainty [4]. PTDs show high current gain and responsivity but the critical limit arises from the intrinsic contradiction between the PTD gain factor and dark current reduces its application [7]. Electron-injection (EI) photon detectors are conceptually designed based on the light detection mechanism in human rod cells [8]. The detector is based on a type-II material system, i.e., InP/GaAsSb/InAlAs/InGaAs and has a cut-off wavelength of 1700 nm. These devices operate in linear mode and provide an avalanche-free gain mechanism [9], [10]. Furthermore, they operate at CMOS compatible bias voltages. Devices with 30 μm active area provide high gain of more than 1000, external dark current of 30 nA, high-speed response ~ 6 ns rise time, together with unity excess noise factor, at bias voltage of -3 V at room temperature [11]. In this paper we report the characteristics of EI detectors with one and two injectors. Simulations are carried out using ATLAS from Silvaco software.

2. Device Structure and Layers

Fig.1 (a) and (b) show the side view and top view schematic diagrams of our proposed detector structure with two injectors.

Fig. 1 (a): Schematic diagram of electron injection detectors with two injectors. The single electron injector doesn't have the 2nd injector (b) top view of the structure.

The two n^+ (10^{19} cm^{-3}) InP injectors are both 550 nm thick. The $\text{In}_{0.52}\text{Al}_{0.48}\text{As}$ etch stop layer is undoped with a thickness of 50 nm. The $\text{GaAs}_{0.52}\text{Sb}_{0.48}$ layer is p^+ doped ($5 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) with 50 nm thickness. The absorber is $\text{In}_{0.53}\text{Ga}_{0.47}\text{As}$ with a thickness of 1000 nm and is n^+ doped (10^{15} cm^{-3}). Substrate is 2000 nm n^+ (10^{18} cm^{-3}) InP.

To obtain the electrical characteristics of the device, the Poisson equation along with the continuity equations for electrons and holes were solved. The analysis incorporated Fermi-Dirac statistics, Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) recombination, Auger recombination, surface recombination, concentration-dependent mobility, and bandgap narrowing models simultaneously.

3. Results and Discussions

When a negative voltage is applied to the injector layer, the InP/GaAsSb junction becomes forward bias. The accumulated electrons in the injector obtain enough energy to get injected from InP layer into the InGaAs absorber. For more negative bias voltages, the current becomes limited by the saturation current of the reverse biased InGaAs/GaAsSb junction and the detector dark

current follows a sublinear relation with bias voltage. When a photon strikes the large InGaAs absorber, an electron/hole pair will be generated in the InGaAs absorber layer. Under negative bias, electrons and holes are separated. The holes are attracted toward the injectors due to internal electric field and get trapped in the GaAsSb trap layers for the period of their lifetime. This leads to a change in the barrier potential and results in electron injection and hence internal amplification in the device. As the electrons pass over the barrier, they lower the local potential and increase the barrier height, opposing the flow of more electrons. This negative feedback mechanism leads to a stable low noise internal amplification [11].

3.1. Dark Current

Fig.2 illustrates dark current versus bias voltage in the two-injector structure in comparison with one injector EI detector. For bias voltage below -0.5 V, the dark current is negligible. With increasing the bias voltage, InP/InAlAs/GaAsSb junction becomes forward bias while the InGaAs/GaAsSb junction is reverse biased. The dark current that passes through the device, is restricted by reverse saturation current of InGaAs/GaAsSb junction.

Fig. 2: Dark current vs. Bias Voltage in single and double injector structures

The dark current of the double injector detector reaches 23 nA at -3 volt while it is 60 nA in one injector structure which shows a 61% reduction in dark current. In our simulations for both the single and double injector structures, the dimensions, the area of injectors and doping concentrations are

assumed the same. For an EI detector with a single injector, as the injector diameter is reduced, hole concentration in the trapping layer, under the injection area, is increased. In the double injector detector however, the hole concentration is spread inside the trapping layers under the inner and the outer injectors. In this condition, for the double injector EI, the barrier potential in conduction band decreases much less than the single injector EI detector, hence dark current in double EI structure is lower than single EI detector.

3.2. Optical Gain

Fig.3 depicts optical gain in the double and the single injector electron-injection detectors as a function of optical power at a bias voltage of -3V.

Fig. 3: Optical Gain vs. Optical Power in single and double injector structures

The wavelength of the optical source is 1550 nm. At low optical power levels, the photogenerated current is limited by the recombination current in the emitter base heterojunction. As optical power increases, the optical gain increases to about 1000. The photo-generated holes are trapped in the trapping layer. Due to the lower hole concentration under the injector areas in the double injector device, and the reduction of barrier lowering as a result of hole entrapment, the gain is lower in the double injector device.

3.3. Rise Time

Fig.4 shows the rise time versus optical power in both structures.

Fig. 4: Rise Time vs Optical Power in single and double injector structures

The rise time is based on when the output signal arises from 10% to 90% of its final value. In Fig.4, it is depicted that the rise time of a double EI detector decreases 4 times at 60pW optical gain in comparison with a single EI detector. As the optical power increases, the rate of electron-hole pair generation is enhanced. As such, more holes are trapped in the GaAsSb trap layer. This phenomenon results in an increase in the electric field so electron velocity increases and rise time improves compared to a single EI device.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, in our proposed two injector EI photon detector, the dark current is reduced in comparison with a single injector photon detector. Although the optical gain in this device is reduced as compared with the single injector device, the rise time of detector is improved which makes it an appropriate candidate for high-speed applications.

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